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CRISTAL

CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

Deliverable 4.4: Application of the generic governance framework and business models to the three case studies (pilots)

**CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport
infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways**

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation/Term	Description
AE	Acoustic Emission (monitoring)
AIPO	Agenzia interregionale per il Fiume Po
BM	Business Model
CATI	Computer-Assisted Telephone Interviewing

CAWI	Computer-Assisted Web Interviewing
ENoLL	European Network of Living Labs
EU	European Union
FOS	Fiber Optic System
GF	Governance Framework
GM	Governance Model
IV	Infrastrutture Venete
IWWT&L	Inland Waterways Transport and Logistic
LL	Living Lab
MIT	Ministero delle Infrastrutture e dei Trasporti
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
SCMS	Synchromodal Corridor Management System
SIR	Subsurface Inspection Radar
TMS	Transport Management System
VNF	Vie Navigable de France
WP	Work Package
WP	Work Packages

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable is part of Work Package 4 (WP4) of the CRISTAL project and focuses on operationalizing governance and business models through stakeholder engagement and applied Living Lab methods. Its goal is to demonstrate how a generic framework can be flexibly adapted to varying national and regional contexts, ensuring local relevance and stakeholder ownership.

This deliverable is essential to the success of the CRISTAL project because it validates and contextualizes the generic governance (T4.2) and business models (T4.3) developed earlier, applying them to real-world scenarios in three different national contexts. The main objective is to create functioning Living Labs and collaboratively agreed implementation plans for deploying the technologies developed under WP2 and the corridor management tools from WP3.

The report presents the results of Living Lab activities conducted in the inland waterways transport and logistics systems of Italy, France, and Poland - specifically focusing on the Po River and Fissero-Tartaro-Canal Bianco network for Italy, the Seine and Moselle rivers for France, and the Vistula River for Poland - and outlines how these processes informed the tailored implementation plans.

The deliverable was jointly produced by SOGESCA, VNF, University of Gdańsk, the University of Antwerp and the Newcastle University. SOGESCA led the capacity building among the consortium partners about the Living Lab setting and implementation, applied the method to the Italian pilot (helped by Union Trasporti, the Italian pilot leader) and made a synthesis of all pilots' activities. VNF coordinated the French stakeholder activities and the LL events implementing. The University of Gdańsk coordinated the Polish activities and the LL event implementing. The University of Antwerp, WP4 leader, supported the method development and defined the Governance Framework of the Technologies. The University of Newcastle University developed the Business Model Canvas of the technologies and the SCMS that have been validated during the Living Lab events. All partners contributed to facilitating Living Lab events, gathering data, and refining the local applications of governance and business frameworks.

The report was developed over an 18-month period, beginning with the setup of national Living Lab cycles in 2023 and progressing through co-creation, validation, and synthesis phases until mid-2025. Data was collected through stakeholder mapping, participatory workshops, digital whiteboards (Miro), interviews, and feedback reports, and analysed using CRISTAL's BM Canvas and governance templates.

The beneficiaries of this work include infrastructure managers, user groups, regional authorities, and national ministries in each pilot country, as well as the broader European inland waterway transport sector.

Key results include:

- A stakeholder-backed Manifesto for Italian IWW development
- Institutional integration of governance tools in France
- Launch of a collaborative platform and policy dialogue in Poland

This deliverable demonstrates the adaptability and effectiveness of CRISTAL's innovations and lays the foundation for further upscaling, institutional adoption, and policy impact. Governance and business models have been tested through stakeholder engagement and application of Living Lab methods. Its goal is to demonstrate how a generic framework can be flexibly adapted to varying national and regional contexts, ensuring local relevance and stakeholder ownership.

1.1. Introduction

The main objective of this deliverable is to apply the Living Lab governance framework and implementation plan in three inland waterway transport case studies: Italy, France, and Poland. From the specific needs of these case studies, the generic governance and business models are tailored to fit the local context. A key outcome of this work is the creation of fully functioning Living Labs and collaboratively agreed implementation plans for the three pilots, supporting the deployment of the technologies developed in WP2 and the corridor management strategy from WP3.

In this subtask, the Living Lab governance model (T4.2) and the developed business models (T4.3) are applied to the three different pilots. This application allows for the inclusion of detailed local context, ensuring that the governance frameworks and business models are effectively customized for each region.

The CRISTAL project (Horizon Europe, Grant Agreement No. 101069838) aims to foster climate-resilient and environmentally sustainable transport infrastructure, with a strong emphasis on inland waterway transport (IWT). Within this context, Work Package 4 (WP4) focuses on developing, testing, and tailoring a generic governance framework and business models suitable for IWT innovation.

Deliverable 4.4 builds upon Deliverables 4.2 and 4.3 by applying these frameworks to real-world conditions in three pilot areas. Each pilot tests and refines the generic models using a Living Lab methodology, ensuring relevance, inclusiveness, and user acceptance.

This document is designed for both European Commission reviewers and consortium partners. It provides a detailed and comprehensive account of how the governance and business models were implemented in practice, presenting not only outcomes but also the processes and stakeholder dynamics that shaped them.

1.2. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2:** Recaps the development of the governance framework and LL methodology.
- **Chapters 3 to 5:** Detail the application and adaptation of the framework in Italy, France, and Poland respectively.
- **Chapter 6:** Summarizes lessons learned, cross-case insights, and implications for wider replication.
- **Chapters 7 to 10:** Include references, appendices, and listings of tables and figures.

2. The living lab framework and implementation plan development.

The CRISTAL project's governance framework and Living Lab (LL) implementation strategy were developed through a combination of theoretical foundations, stakeholder engagement strategies, and iterative pilot feedback. The framework draws from principles defined in Deliverables D4.2 and D4.3 and reflects the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) methodology, emphasizing user-centered innovation in real-life settings.

Figure 1 Conceptual Map: From Generic Governance Tools to Pilot Implementation

2.1. Governance Framework Structure

The generic governance framework includes the following core components:

1. **Introduction and Purpose:** Clarifies the function of governance in enabling climate-resilient, multimodal inland waterway transport.
2. **Governance Principles:** Based on open innovation, business continuity, ICT adequacy, climate adaptation and mitigation, asset management, stakeholder engagement, and social acceptability.
3. **Organizational Structure:** Maps roles and responsibilities across public bodies, infrastructure managers, users, and support entities.
4. **Planning and Coordination:** Outlines mechanisms for operational planning, resource allocation, and conflict resolution.
5. **Information Sharing:** Sets protocols for data standardization, interoperability, and knowledge exchange.

6. **Performance Monitoring:** Introduces KPIs and feedback mechanisms to ensure adaptive learning.
7. **Risk Management:** Focuses on vulnerability assessment and emergency response planning.
8. **Regulatory Compliance:** Aligns framework with EU and national legislation.
9. **Stakeholder Communication:** Promotes inclusive dialogue, transparency, and joint ownership.
10. **Continuous Improvement:** Embeds feedback loops for iterative learning and governance evolution.
11. **Funding and Resource Management:** Ensures financial sustainability and accountability.

2.2. Living Lab Methodology

The LL approach applied in CRISTAL is structured around five phases:

1. **Contextualization:** Defining the pilot scenario, environmental constraints, and stakeholder landscape.
2. **Engagement:** Mapping stakeholders, selecting gate actors, and building trust.
3. **Co-Creation:** Conducting events (workshops, webinars, interviews) using tools like Miro boards and whiteboards to gather insights.
4. **Validation:** Refining BMs and GMs through real-life feedback and scenario testing.
5. **Consolidation:** Producing shared documents (e.g., Manifestos, roadmaps), synthesizing insights, and preparing implementation paths.

2.3. Tools and Templates

To ensure consistency, transparency, and comparability across the three pilot implementations, Work Package 4 developed a robust toolkit of templates and support resources. These tools were designed to be both adaptable and replicable, facilitating stakeholder engagement, data collection, and reporting within each Living Lab process. Key components include:

- **Stakeholder mapping matrices and engagement trackers:** to categorize and monitor stakeholder participation based on influence, interest, and institutional affiliation.
- **Standardized Living Lab event report templates:** used by all pilot coordinators to document workshops, co-creation sessions, and feedback loops, ensuring a uniform structure across countries.
- **Tailored Business Model Canvas templates:** adapted to reflect the needs of the inland waterway transport (IWT) sector and specific CRISTAL innovations, particularly SCMS and infrastructure monitoring technologies.

- **Diagrammatic tools and interactive infographics:** such as stakeholder network maps, LL process flows, and technology validation pathways, developed to support communication and participatory design during workshops.
- **Pre-filled checklists and guides:** including risk assessment protocols, governance readiness indicators, and innovation adoption conditions, which were used to support facilitators and ensure thorough data collection.

These templates not only supported each pilot in planning and executing their Living Lab activities but also provided a shared basis for cross-pilot comparison, ensuring methodological alignment across the project.

2.4. Outputs and Contributions to Pilots

Stakeholder engagement also varied in depth and reach, depending on pilot maturity and institutional integration. The figure below presents a comparison of stakeholder engagement intensity:

Figure 2 Stakeholders Engagement Intensity by Category and pilot

The LL methodology allowed pilots to:

- Surface real implementation barriers and governance gaps
- Adapt generic models to sector-specific and territorial realities
- Validate technology acceptance and economic feasibility
- Establish multi-stakeholder commitment to sustainable IWT

The following chapters demonstrate how this generic approach was locally tailored in each pilot.

3. Application & tailoring of the generic LL governance framework & implementation plan for the Italian pilot

The following section illustrates how the generic Living Lab governance framework and business models were adapted and implemented in the three national pilots. Each pilot applied the CRISTAL methodology to establish a functioning Living Lab, engage relevant stakeholders, and tailor the frameworks to local governance contexts and technological needs. The Italian pilot served as a highly participatory environment to validate both governance structures and technological applications.

Living Lab Settings and tailoring process can be found in Annex 19 and 20.

3.1. Setup of the Living Lab in the Italian Pilot

The Italian pilot focused on the Padano-Veneto Inland Waterways System, encompassing the Po River and its connected canals and ports, including the Fissero-Tartaro-Canal Bianco network. This area represents a key logistical corridor that remains underutilized due to fragmented governance, limited investment, and lack of modal integration. Recognizing these challenges, the pilot launched a Living Lab process facilitated by SOGESCA in close coordination with Unioncamere, Uniontrasporti, AIPO, Infrastrutture Venete, and ENEA.

The Italian Living Lab was designed in alignment with the ENOLL methodology and was structured around two complementary cycles:

- **Governance Cycle:** Aimed at fostering institutional coordination and long-term planning through six co-creation workshops involving representatives from regional governments, transport authorities, industry associations, and civil society.
- **Technology Cycle:** Focused on evaluating the feasibility and applicability of CRISTAL technologies. Specific sessions addressed the Synchronodal Corridor Management System (SCMS), Acoustic Emission (AE) monitoring, Cold Ironing for mooring electrification, Smart Bulletins for digital navigation assistance, and preliminary lab tests of Fiber Optic Systems (FOS).

Stakeholder engagement was carried out using a stakeholder influence-interest matrix, which helped identify gate actors (e.g. user associations) and ensure balanced participation across public and private sectors in engaging manufacturers, logistics operators, and local authorities. Tools such as Miro boards, structured whiteboards, and visual canvases were used to capture insights and encourage interactive dialogue. The participatory approach ensured that stakeholders not only contributed to identifying challenges, but also co-designed actionable solutions aligned with their operational realities.

One of the pilot's strengths was its ability to rebuild trust and communication among institutions that had operated in silos. The Living Lab thus served as a catalyst for a new governance culture in the Italian IWW sector, reintroducing the inland navigation agenda at the national level.

The Italian pilot focused on the Padano-Veneto Inland Waterways System, encompassing the Po River and its connected canals and ports. Recognizing governance fragmentation and underutilization of waterborne transport, a Living Lab process was initiated by SOGESCA in collaboration with Unioncamere, Uniontrasporti, AIPO, Infrastrutture Venete, and ENEA.

The following Figure 3 represents the Living Lab Setting, in particular:

- The Core Elements that are the main Living Lab Objective (1. IWT Harmonized Governance for long-term agreement among stakeholders and 2. Cristal innovation presentation and business model validation). This set includes a sub-set represented by The Governance framework principles that lead Cristal Innovations.
- The General principles that govern this Living Lab are: Open innovation, Business continuity, Adequate ICT, Climate change mitigation, Climate change adaptation, Asset management, Risk assessment - Emergency management, Stakeholders/users involvement , Social acceptability.
- The real-life scenario in which the Living Lab operates that coincides with the pilot scenario and takes in consideration aspects such as: environmental and climate aspects, economic context, legal/administrative framework, social context, water Ways physical aspects (natural and infrastructural), operational aspects, stakeholders involved.

Figure 3 Padano -Veneto Waterways system LL setting

Figure 4 represents the Stakeholders groups and correlations in the Padano-Veneto Inland Waterways System Living Lab.

“At the center are the Users, identified as ship and barge operators, logistics companies (currently utilizing the river), and manufacturers (who could potentially use the river in the future). Surrounding these core users are additional stakeholders following the Quadruple Helix model: user associations, researchers, public authorities, and infrastructure managers. These diagrams illustrate a continuous flow of information, services, and feedback both with the users and among the broader stakeholders’ networks”.
Ortolani, R. (2024). The Living Lab of the Padano-Veneto Inland Waterways System. PORTUSplus Journal, N.17, RETE Publisher, Venice.

Figure 4 Living Lab Stakeholders groups and correlations

Each Stakeholder group has been characterised following the diagram in Figure 5 to position the stakeholders in the Living Lab better and engage them in the proper Living Lab cycle.

Figure 5 Living Lab Stakeholders’ Matrix Analysis

3.2.Updates made to the BMs and GMs to the Italian pilot

This section details how the generic Business Models (BMs) and Governance Models (GMs) developed under WP4 were adapted to the specific context of the Italian pilot. The Living Lab provided a space to test assumptions, integrate user feedback, and align strategies with institutional realities.

- Governance Model:** The Italian LL facilitated the development of a roadmap identifying key governance fragmentation issues. These included overlapping institutional mandates, lack of coordination between regional authorities, and minimal visibility of IWW potential at the national level. The co-creation process highlighted priority areas such as asset management responsibilities, stakeholder communication flows, and multilevel policy alignment.
- Business Models:** SCMS (Synchronodal Corridor Management System) business models were tailored to the Italian context. Emphasis was placed on services like real-time corridor data visualization, predictive maintenance, and modal shift incentives. A freemium model, supported by regional data platforms and public co-funding for early-stage deployment, was explored. Additional considerations included monetization strategies based on data usage, access to analytics, and private logistics partnerships.

The iterative LL process allowed stakeholders to validate these models by stress-testing them through workshops and bilateral exchanges. Cross-sector actors contributed perspectives that shaped refinements, making the outputs more robust and ready for institutional uptake and real-life pilot implementation.

Next to the workshops, the GMs of the SMCS, the Digital Twin, and the Fiber Optic Sensors have been internally validated by using a questionnaire and the updating of the already existing GMs. Some small updates have been made to incorporate more information and features of the technologies in D4.2. No specific updates have been made regarding the application to the Italian pilot case.

No additional updates have been made for the BMs; the methodology of validation can be found in D10.1.

3.3. Implementation plan of technologies in the Italian pilot

The following table summarizes the stakeholder activities conducted in the Italian pilot during the LL process:

Table 1 LL Events in the Italian Pilot

Dates	Activity Type	Frequency	Main Stakeholder Types
24/07/23 27/07/23 08/03/24 15/03/24 27/05/24 05/06/24	Governance Workshops and Manifesto co-creation sessions	6	Public authorities, users' associations, logistic sector, infrastructure managers
25/1/2023 10/05/24 07/06/24 16/05/2025	Technology presentation and validation sessions	4	Infrastructure and Port managers, logistics, manufacturers
27/09/24 26/03/25	Manifesto Presentation	2	Ministry and Cross-sector actors
29/05/25	Final In-person event in Mantua	1	All Stakeholders Groups

Each technology was introduced in stakeholder sessions, feedback was collected, and pilot-specific adaptation needs were documented. A final event in Mantua in May 2025 marked the conclusion of this phase.

Living Lab Reflections:

Positive experiences from the Italian Living Lab included a collaborative approach among previously fragmented stakeholders, leading to the creation of a unique and coordinated critical mass. This cohesion enabled broader engagement and more representative feedback on governance and technology topics. A key lesson learned was the systemic nature of inland waterway transport—its success depends on

multiple interlinked factors and thus requires a systemic approach. However, the LL process also encountered challenges. The Italian IWW sector is relatively small and close-knit, which occasionally resulted in misunderstandings or friction between groups during participatory events. A lesson drawn from this is the importance of designing stakeholder engagement in a way that encourages open and comfortable dialogue. Specifically, events should target the appropriate stakeholder group per topic to ensure productive and focused input; engaging all parties in every event is not always fruitful.

LL Outputs:

1. Qualitative validation of CRISTAL technologies by stakeholders
2. Renewed attention and political visibility for the Italian IWWT system
3. Co-creation of the "Manifesto for Sustainable Development of the Padano-Veneto IWW"

3.3.1 Qualitative validation of CRISTAL technologies by stakeholders

The Italian pilot organises three online event to validate and present the Cristal model technologies.

The first technology event presented the feasibility study of the cold ironing carried out by Infrastrutture Venete only, while during the other two events Cristal project partners presented the SCMS platform together with the other feeding technologies as the FOS, the acoustic emission and the Smart bulletin (Annexes 7 and 8). After the presentation, stakeholders answered to a survey to assess the possible impact of the technologies on the field and to validate the SCMA Business model (Annex 6).

Figure 6 Screenshot of the survey performed with Mentimeter about the SCMS and Smart Bulletin Technologies impact assessment

Figure 7 Screenshot of the survey performed with Mentimeter about all the Technologies impact assessment

The CRISTAL SCMS Business Model Canvas

Figure 8 The Cristal SCMS Business Model Canvas

Figure 9 Screenshot of the survey performed with Slido to validate the SCMS Business Model

3.3.2. Co-creation of the "Manifesto for Sustainable Development of the Padano-Veneto IWW"

The Manifesto (Annex 1) is a document co-created with various stakeholders' groups. At its core, the document presents a comprehensive list of issues, proposed solutions, and the responsible recipient identified by stakeholders of the Padano-Veneto Waterways System.

The strength of this document lies in the fact that, for the first time, all major daily challenges faced by different actors have been clearly outlined, discussed, and shared from each stakeholder's perspective.

Figure 10 Example of co-creation tool with Stakeholders to analyse one specific issue

Table 2 Tabulation and translation in English of the diagram in Figure 10

Accessibility and use of ports and infrastructure		
USERS PROBLEMS	USERS PROPOSED SOLUTIONS	PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION PROPOSED SOLUTIONS
Numerous navigation locks have been inaccessible due to maintenance needs (Valle et al.) and difficult access to Porto Garibaldi. Difficult access from the Pontelagoscuero basin to the port. Partnerships launched for the Governolo basin. Significant reduction in water flow. Hydraulic safety problems in the Ferrarese Waterway	A maintenance plan that considers the priorities of intervention is needed	Access to Porto Garibaldi.
	Allocate resources and responsibilities.	Financing for the Ferrarese waterway
		Design for the maintenance of the Valle Lepri basin is in progress.
Shallow waters with difficulty for navigation on the Po and in some moorings	Coordination between different responsible bodies and plan with chronological schedule of works.	Strategies that allow to intercept private resources and build public/private partnerships.
	Encourage partnerships and agreements that allow a unified management of activities	Project in collaboration with AIPO and outsourcing of dredging activities.

	Make the bulletin of the seabed and hydrometers more efficient.	
	Discounting costs (budget for dredging must increase).	
Fragmentation in the management of landings, lack of maintenance and services (electricity, toilets, waste removal, drinking water supply)	Shared service charter for mooring points.	
	Centralize management responsibilities or establish management partnerships or provide technical and economic support to small municipalities.	
	Transparency and uniformity of mooring costs.	
	Development of cold ironing.	
Some bridges with insufficient light	-	-
Lack of information of tourist interest on the piers	Portolano for the Fissero Tartaro Canalbianco and Ferrara Waterways.	
	Information of tourist interest at the piers	

The Manifesto for the Sustainable Development of the Padano-Veneto IWW co-created, endorsed by 35+ stakeholders and submitted to the Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport, serving as a reference document for national dialogue and investment strategies.¹

Manifesto for the Sustainable Development of the Padano-Veneto Inland Waterways System. Short and Medium-Term Actions for a Long-Term Vision

Promoted by the European CRISTAL Project [Project: 101069838 — CRISTAL — HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01] and Developed in Collaboration with Stakeholders of the Padano-Veneto Inland Waterway System.

Figure 11 Manifesto for the sustainable development of the Padano-Veneto Inland Waterways System

¹ CRISTAL Project. Manifesto per lo sviluppo sostenibile del sistema idroviario Padano-Veneto, 2024. https://www.cristal-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/Manifesto_IWS.pdf

3.3.3 Renewed attention and political visibility for the Italian IWWT system

On March 26th 2025 the Italian Pilot partners presented at The Ministry of Infrastructures and Transports in Rome the Manifesto (Annex 1) and the Paper published on the international Journal Portus Plus n.117/2024 (Annex 2) about the Living Lab experience in the Padano Veneto Waterways system as in Figure 13.

Figure 13 Presentation of the Manifesto at the MIT Ministry of Infrastructures and Transport in Rome on March 26th, 2025

This event has been crucial to put in light several cronical problems and to put in contact the Ministry with the key Stakeholders.

During the in-person event held in Mantua on May 29th, a delegation of Stakeholders' representatives met two fonctionaires of the Ministry to talk about one of the main problems raised in the Manifesto, the incentives related problem, to initiate a productive dialog.

In Annex 5 there are the Findings and insight after the Hydrobonus discussion between Stakeholders and Ministry of Infrastructures and transport in Mantua, sent to the Ministry.

The following three pictures on Figure 14,15 and 16 the Italian pilot team facilitates the dialogue about incentives between the Public Functionaries and the stakeholders and organises the final events in Mantua (in Annex 4 there is the presentation of the Living Lab process and the Manifesto during the Mantua in-person final event).

Figure 14 Stakeholders round table about incentives with Ministry in Mantua on May 29th, 2025

Figure 16 The Cristal Project's Italian team during the in-person event in Mantua on May 29th, 2025

Figure 15 Audience of the in-person event in Mantua on May 29th, 2025

Figure 17 gives a qualitative estimation of what will happen to the chronic problems of the Padano-Veneto Inland Waterways System if the Manifesto's proposed solutions were implemented.

ITEM	CHRONIC PROBLEMS	CURRENT LEVEL OF SEVERITY	PROBABILITY OF IMPLEMENTING THE MANIFESTO'S ACTIONS	FORESEEN LEVEL OF SEVERITY AFTER IMPLEMENTING MANIFESTO'S ACTIONS
1	Fragmented Governance, difficulties in communications among stakeholders	○	75%	○
2	Inadequacy of the Waterway infrastructure for goods transportation	○	60%	○
3	Lack of infrastructure maintenance	○	60%	○
4	Need of a Users' Consortium	○	90%	○
5	Lack of national employment contract for river navigation workers	○	80%	○
6	Shortage of personnel	○	50%	○
7	Regulatory sector-related issues and lack of adequate incentives	○	60%	○

Figure 17 Summary of the existing chronic problems of the Padano-Veneto Inland Waterways System and the expected level of resolution after implementing the Manifesto's proposed solutions²

3.3.4 LL Legacy in Real-Life Settings:

- Stakeholders felt heard and acknowledged, with improved chances of their needs being addressed
- The Ministry of Infrastructure now has a clear reference group for IWW dialogue
- Greater cohesion among stakeholders, supporting future advocacy and policy development

² Ortolani, R. (2024). The Living Lab of the Padano-Veneto Inland Waterways System. PORTUSplus Journal, N.17, RETE Publisher, Venice. <https://portusplus.org/index.php/pp/article/view/304>

4. Application & tailoring of the generic LL governance framework & implementation plan for the French pilot

The French inland waterway system plays a critical role in freight mobility and multimodal logistics, particularly across the Seine and Moselle River corridors. These waterways serve both commercial transport and recreational users and are managed by Voies navigables de France (VNF). The French pilot in CRISTAL focuses on leveraging existing stakeholder networks and VNF governance processes to validate and adapt new technologies. Within this complex and mature IWWT context, the Living Lab approach aims to reinforce cooperation among actors and co-develop practical tools that support operational improvements and long-term governance cohesion.

4.1. Setup of the LL in French pilot

The French pilot was coordinated by Voies navigables de France (VNF) and focused on technological validation through co-creation with internal and external stakeholders. Rather than organizing independent LL events, the approach leveraged regular institutional meetings with stakeholder groups, integrating CRISTAL technology testing and feedback activities into VNF's governance cycle. The approach has been developed to maximise the involvement of stakeholders that are difficult to reach.

The objective was triple:

- For technology providers to ensure that technologies met the end-users needs
- For infrastructure manager to evidence transparency to its end-users
- For end-user to bring up needs

To maximise feedback, VNF chose to address each technology to its natural end-user. The repartition has been developed as follows:

Figure 18: Scheme of VNF Living Lab plan (source: VNF)

Following this plan, three dedicated workshops between October 2024 and April 2025 targeted distinct stakeholder categories, including freight operators, leisure boaters, public authorities, and VNF engineers. To maximise the feedback, not all technologies were presented to every stakeholder type. VNF presented

SCMS, CEDRE, Digital Twins, Acoustic Emission (AE) systems, and Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) technologies to its potential clients.

The workshops applied structured participatory tools (e.g. Miro boards, post-it canvases) and produced valuable input for technology adaptation.

In addition to these events, informal feedback was collected from VNF's internal departments, including its asset management and maintenance teams. These inputs were instrumental in shaping technology requirements, integration expectations, and identifying real-world operational scenarios where innovations could be deployed.

A notable strength of the French LL setup was its integration into VNF's existing governance cycles, enhancing continuity and institutional ownership. However, this approach also presented challenges, particularly in shaping agendas that served both CRISTAL's experimental objectives and VNF's day-to-day management needs.

Overall, the LL structure allowed for multi-actor participation and enabled dialogue across silos within VNF and its external stakeholders. This setup supported not only validation of specific technologies, but also the emergence of a more collaborative culture around innovation adoption in French IWW governance.

4.2. Updates made to the BMs and GMs to the French pilot

Stakeholders provided detailed feedback on the usability, integration potential, and economic implications of the technologies:

- **SCMS:** Participants emphasized the importance of alert systems, data interoperability with platforms like EuRIS or PC Navigo, and the need for a viable economic model. Freight groups suggested integration with Transport Management Systems (TMS), while leisure users prioritized real-time notifications.
- **CEDRE:** Stakeholders highlighted its potential to streamline administrative procedures and reduce freight costs. Key concerns included data confidentiality, interoperability, and the development of differentiated interfaces for industrial and artisanal operators.

These insights informed an initial tailoring of business models around user-specific value propositions, including operational cost savings, risk mitigation, and improved navigability.

Additionally, the GMs of the technologies researched in this pilot (the SCMS, the Digital Twin, the Acoustic Emission Technology, and the Subsurface Radar Inspection Technology) have also been internally validated via a questionnaire and updating the existing GMs. Some small updates have been made to incorporate more information and features of the technologies in D4.2. No specific updates have been made regarding the application to the French pilot case.

No additional updates have been made for the BMs; the methodology of validation can be found in D1

4.3. Implementation plan of technologies in the French pilot

The table below summarizes LL activities embedded in VNF stakeholder forums:

Table 3 LL Events in the French Pilot

Dates	Forum/Event	Focus Technologies	Stakeholders
09/10/24	Comité National des Usagers	SCMS, CEDRE	Freight, leisure operators, barge owners
15/10/24	Comité des ingénieurs VNF	AE, SIR, Digital Twin	Technical and engineering staff
16/04/25	Maintenance Staff Roundtable	AE, SIR, Digital Twin	Technical and maintenance staff

The French Living Lab events (Annexes 11) were implemented during already scheduled stakeholder meetings. French IWT stakeholders typically meet to discuss navigational issues or infrastructure needs. By integrating the CRISTAL Living Lab topics into these existing forums, participants were able to brainstorm potential improvements, become acquainted with CRISTAL technologies, and engage in dialogue with stakeholders they may not regularly collaborate with.

While this format allowed for efficient access to relevant audiences, it also limited the project team's ability to fully design workshop content and objectives in advance, as CRISTAL activities had to align with pre-existing meeting agendas. To tackle this challenge, VNF developed a methodology.

First, all technology providers were interviewed to establish a consistent presentation of their respective technologies. Since the timelines of CRISTAL and VNF were not always aligned, most technologies did not yet have concrete results to showcase during the Living Lab. As a result, VNF chose to present each technology as if it were already functioning as intended. The Living Lab also served as an opportunity to gather new functional requirements, which proved to be a valuable outcome for the CRISTAL project

Second, since not all work packages had clearly defined their expected outcomes from the Living Lab, VNF, in coordination with other work package leaders, developed a list of questions to address as many potential needs as possible.

SCMS:

Questions:

- Will such a system give you greater confidence in your mobility on the waterways? Adapt / increase your traffic? Can you provide a rough estimation (%)?
- How beneficial to your logistic operations do you consider each of the four components of SCMS (1. Early alert & notification system, 2. Disruption impact assessment, 3. Synchromodal rerouting tool, 4. Observatory)? (scale e.g. 1 to 5)
- What types of data and visualizations included in SCMS would be most useful to you (location of alerts on map, list of alerts per time period (from-until), river infrastructure visualization on map, alternative routes visualization on map (including road-rail), infrastructure metrics (e.g. locks % availability per year), operational metrics, river infrastructure index)? (put in order from the most important to the less important)
- What additional functionality/visualizations-data would you like to see in the SCMS? (free text)
- Do you have any suggestions for improving the user interface and overall experience of the SCMS? (free text)
- How do you see the impact of SCMS on the efficiency of your supply chain? (scale e.g. 1 to 10, from positive to negative)
- To what extent do you think that the SCMS could improve your ability to respond to logistical disruptions (resilience)? (scale e.g. 1 to 5)
- How could SCMS help to reduce your operational costs and CO2 emissions?
- How would you rate the importance of SCMS interoperability and flexibility for your business (e.g. connection to existing platforms like EURIS)? (scale e.g. 1 to 10, from positive to negative)
- What would be the main barriers to SCMS adoption in your organisation? (free text)
- What challenges do you expect to encounter when integrating the SCMS into your current processes? (free text)

Figure 19 Example of refined questions for the 9th of October 2024 Living Lab in-person session organised by VNF (Annex 14)

Third, dedicated sessions were organized. Each technology was allocated 30 minutes, consisting of a brief presentation followed by in-depth discussions in small groups to address the predefined questions. This approach led to the following outcomes (Annex 11.3):

- Acoustic Emission (AE) technology enables early detection of invisible anomalies and continuous monitoring, reducing manual inspections for locks, hydraulic systems, and bridges. However, noise interference complicates sound interpretation, and implementation requires time for installation and data analysis. For effective adoption, the system must be simple, standardized, and supported by proper training. Engineers are concerned about costs, maintenance, and sensor replacement procedures. AE offers complementary—not replacement—expertise to technicians, though it remains more curative than preventive, with alternatives like underwater drones and manual inspections still being considered.
- Participants see SIR technology as useful for sensitive dams, aqueducts, levees, and hydraulic structures, though its application to canals may be time-consuming. Key challenges include the inability to inspect some underwater areas and the lengthy diagnostic process. The technology could support maintenance planning and improve the reliability of locks and waterways by providing detailed structural data before scheduled downtimes. Essential features include waterproofing and precise material layer detection. Participants suggest outsourcing or assigning a national specialized team, noting that while SIR could prevent last-minute repairs, it might also increase planned interventions.
- The Digital Twin (DT) is seen as a potential management and decision-support tool for the hydraulic network, allowing information integration and visualization to aid maintenance and operations. Although similar to existing systems like SCADA, the DT could add value by supporting predictive analysis—if a sufficient historical database is developed. Its effectiveness would increase when combined with AE and SIR technologies, though modeling every lock is unrealistic. Participants note the DT's benefits for anticipation and communication but question its added value over sensor data and its impact on costs. They request concrete, practical examples of implementation.

Despite this constraint, the main outcome of the French LL process was raising awareness and generating interest around CRISTAL technologies.

The most tangible legacy of the French LL was the initiation of a collaborative environment in which technology development can proceed with early stakeholder involvement and feedback.

VNF identified pilot use cases (e.g. locks, bridges, dams) where AE and SIR could be tested further, and suggested a modular approach for Digital Twin deployment, starting with hydraulic data integration.

5. Application & tailoring of the generic LL governance framework & implementation plan for the Polish pilot

The Polish pilot represents the third national testbed for implementing CRISTAL's Living Lab methodology and adapting the generic governance and business models. Building on the lessons learned from Italy and France, this pilot aims to assess the feasibility and relevance of the proposed models in the Polish inland waterway context. While it is in an earlier phase of deployment, the groundwork has been laid to initiate a functioning Living Lab supported by national and regional stakeholders.

5.1. Setup of the LL in the Polish pilot

The Polish Living Lab, organized under the framework of the CRISTAL Project, took place on Monday, April 14, 2025, at the Faculty of Economics, University of Gdańsk in Sopot. The event was hosted by the University of Gdańsk and brought together a wide range of stakeholders, including representatives from the logistics and shipping industries, infrastructure and port authorities, skippers, academia, and governmental institutions (Annex 16).

The main objective of the meeting was to assess the outcomes of the pilot voyages conducted within the CRISTAL Project on Polish inland waterways (IWW). Additionally, the event aimed to raise awareness about the development potential of IWT in the context of the EU's green transition, highlighting key challenges, barriers, and opportunities.

5.1.1 Participants

The Living Lab welcomed over 20 representatives from relevant stakeholder groups, such as logistics operators, port authorities, governmental ministries, inland navigation companies, technology providers, and universities. These participants actively contributed to the discussion, bringing practical experience and institutional perspectives.

Figure 20 Living Lab Participants

Figure 21 Participants structure by Stakeholders Group

5.2. Updates made to the BMs and GMs to the Polish pilot.

Initial adaptation of the governance and business models has focused on localizing the following elements:

- Tailoring the governance framework to reflect Poland’s regulatory and institutional context, particularly focusing on coordination between national and regional transport authorities.
- Early-stage discussion of business model feasibility for SCMS and sensor-based technologies, including opportunities for public-private partnerships and logistics chain optimization.

The process has included desk research and bilateral interviews to assess the state of play and build the foundation for participatory validation sessions.

Additionally, the GMs of the SCMS, Digital Twin and the other technologies have been internally validated by using a questionnaire and by updating the already existing GMs. Some small updates have been made to incorporate more information and features of the technologies in D4.2. No specific updates have been made regarding the application to the French pilot case.

No additional updates have been made for the BMs; the methodology of validation can be found in D10.1.

5.3. Implementation plan of technologies in the Polish pilot

5.3.1 Event Agenda and Proceedings

The meeting agenda was structured around three primary components, each addressing a different facet of the CRISTAL Project's implementation and strategic objectives for inland navigation in Poland.

Research Presentation: Perception and Socio-Economic Insights

The opening session was led by Ernest Czermanski and Marta Waldmann, who introduced the foundational assumptions of the CRISTAL Project and the Living Lab methodology. This was followed by a comprehensive presentation by Tomasz Czuba, summarizing the findings of Deliverable 9.3—Perception of the Vistula River and Inland Navigation in Poland. The research, conducted in January 2025, was a collaborative effort by Tomasz Czuba, Barbara Pawłowska, and Ernest Czermanski.

The study examined attitudes towards the use of the Vistula River across three key respondent groups: the general public (n=1200), stakeholders from the transport sector (n=600), and tourism professionals (n=600). Data was gathered using both CAWI and CATI methodologies.

Findings indicated that more than half of the general public was aware of the navigability potential of the Vistula River, with strong support for using the river for freight (60%), tourism (61%), and recreational activities (59%). Despite limited personal engagement with the river, the public regarded it as an ecologically beneficial and economically viable alternative to road transport. Concerns raised included risks to aquatic ecosystems, pollution, and noise levels.

Stakeholders from the transport sector echoed support for expanding IWT, emphasizing the environmental and logistical advantages. However, they underlined several critical barriers, including inadequate infrastructure, lack of modernization, and seasonal unreliability of river depth.

Institutional and tourism stakeholders highlighted the broader socio-economic impact of revitalizing the Vistula, noting potential benefits for regional development and tourism. A shared conclusion was that such revitalization should be led and financed by central government authorities. The research revealed that while ecological concerns exist, the overall risk was perceived as manageable through adequate regulation.

In closing, it was agreed that developing inland navigation on the Vistula is not only a question of transport diversification, but a strategic component of Poland's sustainable development policy.

Technology Feedback and Evaluation

The second session was dedicated to the usability and perception of technologies introduced within the CRISTAL Project. A structured panel session and targeted questionnaire allowed stakeholders to reflect on technological aspects such as system integration, digitalization, and automation.

Stakeholders responded with cautious optimism. There was a general belief that a unified technological system could significantly enhance the performance and reliability of IWW transport, particularly under conditions of disruption caused by weather events or human error. Many noted the potential for

technology to act as a cohesive layer across multimodal networks—including roads, railways, and inland waterways.

Nonetheless, participants emphasized that technology alone would not overcome existing structural barriers. Real progress would require parallel efforts in infrastructure modernization, regulatory reform, and better institutional coordination. Views were more reserved regarding the role of technology in increasing recycling efficiency or facilitating legal compliance, suggesting that policy and planning remain critical levers.

Figure 22 Business Model Canvas presentation and evaluation

The consensus was that while innovation plays an enabling role, it must be embedded within a broader strategic framework, supported by adequate governance and investment.

Stakeholder Discussion Panel: Operational Challenges and Future Outlook

The final and most interactive part of the event was a stakeholder panel discussion, based on insights from four pilot voyages executed by VAN Cargo S.A. Grzegorz Jagusiak presented a detailed operational summary of each pilot, outlining the practical challenges encountered—primarily low water levels, inadequate depth, and infrastructure bottlenecks.

A number of critical issues emerged from the discussion:

- **Infrastructure Shortcomings:** The limited navigability of the Vistula due to low and unpredictable water levels was cited as a primary barrier. Business representatives noted that logistics operations require consistency, which current river conditions cannot guarantee.
- **Incompatible Urban Development:** Concerns were raised about residential developments encroaching on riverside logistics zones. Katarzyna Szczycińska from the Port of Gdańsk

emphasized the need for regulatory protections to safeguard future port operations from urban expansion.

- **Institutional Fragmentation:** Confusion over institutional responsibility was highlighted. While the public perceives “the government” as accountable, in practice, it is the Ministry of Infrastructure’s Department of Maritime Economy and Inland Navigation. Participants called for clearer governance and policy alignment.
- **Environmental and NGO Pressures:** While NGOs were acknowledged as critical stakeholders in promoting ecological standards, several cases were mentioned in which their intervention led to setbacks or cost escalations. The need for balanced engagement was stressed.
- **Financial Uncertainty:** The lack of stable, multiyear funding mechanisms was a recurrent theme. Annual budgets and short planning cycles were seen as obstacles to achieving long-term investment in inland waterways.

Despite these challenges, there was broad consensus on the strategic importance of revitalizing IWT in Poland. Participants supported a coordinated, national-level approach to infrastructure development, aligned with sustainability goals and multimodal logistics integration.

Figure 23 Open discussion panel

5.3.2 Main considerations from the Polish Living Lab implementation

The Living Lab in Poland has highlighted the considerable potential of inland waterway transport to contribute to sustainable logistics in the EU. However, realizing this potential depends on a coordinated national strategy, supported by stable financing, technological innovation, and regulatory clarity. The CRISTAL Project provides a valuable foundation for this transformation, but further actions are needed to unlock the full benefits of Poland’s river systems.

6. Conclusions

The implementation of the CRISTAL generic governance framework and business models through the Living Lab approach has demonstrated its flexibility and adaptability across diverse territorial and regulatory contexts. Despite each pilot area exhibiting unique infrastructural, institutional, and stakeholder characteristics, the core methodology proved effective in catalysing engagement, supporting technology validation, and surfacing governance and business model challenges.

Key cross-pilot conclusions include:

1. **Living Lab as a Catalyst for Governance Reform:** In both Italy and France, the LL process allowed stakeholders to collectively identify long-standing governance gaps. The Italian pilot's Manifesto is a significant outcome, formally recognized by regional and national authorities. In France, VNF embedded CRISTAL discussions into existing structures, ensuring institutional continuity and internal ownership.
2. **Technology Validation Requires Deep Contextualization:** Technologies such as SCMS, AE, and SIR triggered robust discussions about operability, integration with existing systems (e.g., EuRIS, TMS), and practical deployment conditions. Local technical standards, administrative procedures, and end-user digital readiness shaped how each pilot approached implementation.
3. **Business Models Must Reflect Stakeholder Diversity:** The heterogeneity of users—from commercial freight operators to leisure navigation groups—necessitates modular, flexible business models. In France, the economic viability of multimodal rerouting required further analysis; in Italy, user feedback contributed directly to BM Canvas refinement.
4. **Stakeholder Trust is a Precondition for Participation:** The Italian and French pilots confirmed the importance of neutral facilitation, tailored communication, and the provision of short-term incentives (e.g. analysis reports, policy advocacy) to sustain engagement.
5. **Preliminary Polish Activities Confirm Transferability:** While still ongoing, the Polish pilot confirms the relevance of the generic framework. Early stakeholder engagement, alignment with national policy structures, and SCMS interest signal positive conditions for LL success.

Challenges Encountered and Lessons Learned:

- One of the main difficulties was aligning stakeholder schedules and institutional engagement timelines with the project calendar. In Italy and Poland, delays in initial contacts were mitigated by leveraging pre-existing institutional relationships. In France, embedding activities into VNF's internal schedule proved efficient and is considered a best practice for future efforts.
- Coordinating diverse levels of technical knowledge among stakeholders also presented a challenge. This was addressed by adapting the communication tools and pacing of the workshops, and by preparing simplified technology briefs in advance.
- In Poland, establishing the Living Lab structure while still conducting stakeholder mapping posed sequencing challenges. For future replications, a two-step pre-engagement phase may be introduced to clarify roles and expectations ahead of pilot deployment.

Good Practices to Establish:

- Integrating Living Lab activities into institutional routines and formal bodies (e.g., technical boards, user committees) enhances participation and continuity.
- Using collaborative digital tools (e.g. Miro, shared canvases) combined with in-person facilitation supports inclusive co-creation.
- Allowing flexibility in governance and business model templates encourages local ownership and better reflects stakeholder needs.

Final Reflections:

The Living Lab method enabled CRISTAL to move beyond theoretical models to real-world application, providing pathways for governance harmonization, innovation validation, and co-created development strategies. As the pilots move toward demonstration and upscaling, these foundations will support further institutionalization of IWT as a resilient and sustainable transport mode in Europe.

7. References

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- ENoLL. The European Network of Living Labs. <https://enoll.org>

8. Appendices

The D4.4 report refers to materials used during individual LLs. These materials are attached as separate files, as listed below³.

Italian pilot documents:

1. The Manifesto for the sustainable development of the Padano-Veneto Inland Waterways system
2. The Living Lab of the Padano-Veneto Inland Waterways System. An Innovative Governance for Sustainable Development and Climate Resilience_Portus plus Journal Article
3. No.4 Events reports examples (3.1-3.2-3.3-3.4)
4. Presentations of Living Lab and Manifesto in Mantua in person final event
5. Findings and insight after the Hydrobonus discussion between Stakeholders and Ministry of Infrastructures and transport in Mantua
6. SCMS BM Validation poll results
7. Survey on WP3 questions and smart bulletin
8. Survey on WP4 and WP6 questions

 Annex 1. Manifesto for the sustainable development of the Padano Veneto Inland Waterways system

 Annex 2. The Living Lab of the Padano-Veneto Inland Waterways System. An Innovative Governance for Sustainable Development and Climate Resilience Portus plus Journal Article

 Annex 3.1. 2023.07.24 - LL activity report

 Annex 3.2. 2023.07.27 - LL activity report

 Annex 3.3. 2023.25.01 - LL activity report

 Annex 3.4. 2024.07.09 - LL activity report

 Annex 4. 2025.05.29 - Presentation of Living Lab and Manifesto in Mantua in person final event

 Annex 5. Findings and insight after the Hydrobonus discussion between Stakeholders and Ministry of Infrastructures and transport in Mantua

 Annex 6. SCMC BM Validation_poll-results

 Annex 7. Survey on WP3 questions and smart bulletin

 Annex 8. Survey WP4-WP6 questions

French pilot documents:

9. Atelier VNF presentation LGI (event of 9.10.24)
10. Atelier VNF presentation LGI (event of 15.10.24)
11. No.3 Events reports (11.1-11.2-11.3)
12. Feedback external stakeholders
13. Feedback internal stakeholders
14. English translation of Stakeholders questions (event of 9.10.24)
15. English translation of Stakeholders questions (event of 15.10.24)

³ Due to the inability to attach such a large number of files in the Sygma system, they are available upon request.

- Annex 9. Atelier VNF présentation LGI 09-10-2024VF
- Annex 10. Atelier VNF présentation LGI 15-10-2024 v02
- Annex 11.1. 2024.10.09 - LL activity report
- Annex 11.2. 2024.10.15 - LL activity report
- Annex 11.3. 2025.04.16 - LL activity report
- Annex 12. 241009_Feedbacks_External_Stakeholders_FR_EN
- Annex 13. 241015_Feedbacks_Internal_Stakeholders_FR_EN
- Annex 14. Traduction Questions 09.10.2024
- Annex 15. Traduction Questions 15.10.2024

Polish pilot documents:

- 16. No.1 Event report
- 17. Technologies presentation and validation test

- Annex 16. Cristal_Polish LL Report
- Annex 17. Technologies presentation and validation test

Transversal documents:

- 18. Cristal architecture presentation
- 19. Webinar about Living Lab Methodology to pilots lead by SOGESCA
- 20. Planning and Tailoring LL process with the three pilots lead by SOGESCA

- Annex 18. Cristal architecture presentation
- Annex 19. 2023.12.04 - Webinar about Living Lab Methodology to pilots lead by SOGESCA
- Annex 20. 2025.04.15 - Planning and Tailoring LL process with the three pilots lead by SOGESCA

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